

Integrating Single-Cell Multi-Omics and Prior Biological Knowledge for a Functional Characterization of the Immune System

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Abstract

The immune system comprises diverse specialized cell types that cooperate to defend the host against a wide range of pathogenic threats. Recent advancements in single-cell and spatial multi-omics technologies provide rich information about the molecular state of immune cells. Here, we review how the integration of single-cell and spatial multi-omics data with prior knowledge - gathered from decades of detailed biochemical studies - allows us to obtain functional insights, focusing on gene regulatory processes and cell-cell interactions. We present diverse applications in immunology and critically assess underlying assumptions and limitations. Finally, we offer a perspective on the ongoing technological and algorithmic developments that promise to get us closer to a systemic mechanistic understanding of the immune system.

Keywords: single-cell and spatial multi-omics, prior knowledge, computational modeling, machine learning, systems immunology

Introduction

The immune system serves as a prime example of a complex adaptive system, encompassing numerous components whose interactions facilitate appropriate responses to a broad array of pathogenic challenges while maintaining immunological tolerance to harmless and self antigens. This complexity makes it difficult to quantitatively describe how genetic and environmental factors give rise to the heterogeneity in human responses to pathogens ¹, vaccines ², other immunotherapies ³, or harmless antigens in the case of autoimmune disease ⁴. Which immune processes might underlie such variations can be inferred from the analysis of omics data, thereby informing hypothesis generation and computational mechanistic modeling which ultimately guides further experimental studies ^{5,6}.

In recent years, the omics toolbox has gained powerful additions driven by innovations in the single-cell and spatial multi-omics field (Fig. 1). These innovations are expanding the scope of studies in at least two dimensions: (1) Increasing the breadth and depth of information we get per cell as we can jointly measure several molecular layers, such as the transcriptome and chromatin accessibility ⁷, or measure molecular layers while preserving the spatial context ⁸; (2) Decreasing the cost and effort required to perform single-cell experiments, enabling the study of larger patient cohorts ⁹⁻¹¹.

Fig 1: Cycle of biological knowledge and computational methods driven by technological progress. *Technological advancements enable profiling of more samples and molecular layers, prompting the development of novel computational methods which help us to devise hypotheses about the mechanisms underlying complex immunological phenomena. Experimental validation of those hypotheses improves our prior knowledge which in turn helps us to develop better computational methods.*

However, merely increasing the number of data points does not improve our understanding of immunology. Instead, we need algorithms that transform raw data into human-interpretable representations and actionable hypotheses. One computational strategy is to systematically leverage existing biological knowledge from decades of molecular and genomic research. Biological databases catalog a vast amount of knowledge ranging from information about genes (e.g. variants, orthology relationships)¹² and proteins (e.g. structure, binding partners, subcellular localization, catalyzed reactions)¹³⁻¹⁵ to information on cell types and tissues (e.g. marker genes, location)^{9,11} ([Fig. 1](#)). Leveraging this knowledge, we can generate human-interpretable representations ([Fig. 2](#)). Instead of using a 20,000-dimensional gene expression vector, we can for example describe cells, clusters, or samples by inferring the activity of key transcription factors¹⁶, signaling pathways¹⁷, or cell-cell communication events¹⁸, ultimately helping us to better understand what drives different functional outcomes.

Here, we review the use of these strategies, to examine immune system function from two intertwined angles: (1) intracellular processes, focusing on transcriptional regulation & signaling; and (2) intercellular processes, emphasizing cell-cell interactions and spatial organization. The reader can find elsewhere reviews of single-cell data generation^{19,20}, experimental design²¹, or data analysis upstream of these approaches²²⁻²⁴. We focus on methods that integrate scRNA-seq, paired scRNA and ATAC-seq, and spatially resolved transcriptomics data with prior knowledge, and we also provide a brief primer on adaptive immune repertoire analyses from scV(D)J-seq (see [Box 1](#)). We showcase these methods using examples from cancer, aging, infectious disease, and chronic inflammation. To guide researchers in using the discussed methods, we provide practical considerations and discuss inherent limitations. We conclude the review by speculating how future technological and algorithmic innovations might mitigate these shortcomings.

Fig 2: Mechanistic representations for single-cell data. Combining prior knowledge with diverse molecular layers and spatial information to obtain functional insights at the level of single cells, clusters, and samples, which ultimately helps to create more informative contrasts between different conditions. Abbreviations: transcription factor (TF), peptide-major histocompatibility complex (pMHC), T cell antigen receptor (TCR), B cell antigen receptor (BCR), antigen (Ag).

Intracellular Processes

The increasing throughput of single-cell technologies has enabled the detailed study of cell populations present within specific organs in various disease contexts, best represented by the generation of large-scale atlases⁹⁻¹¹. To link single-cell studies to

our existing biological knowledge, a crucial step is the annotation of cells ²³. Given its importance, various methods have been developed to automatically annotate single-cell data using existing high-quality datasets as reference (see [Box 2](#)).

Yet cell type labels offer only limited insight as they do not describe *per se* the functional activities of a cell. To derive functional insights from scRNA-seq data, we can harness prior knowledge in the form of annotated gene sets, i.e. groups of genes with a common function. Here, we start by describing how gene sets can be used to estimate the activity of functional modules or programs ([Fig. 3, A](#)), such as metabolic pathways or immune functions. Then, we describe how we can infer upstream processes including transcription factor (TF) activity, gene regulatory networks (GRNs), and signaling cascade activity ([Fig. 3, B-D](#)). Finally, we explore methods to infer which intercellular signaling events could have caused the intracellular processes ([Fig. 3, E](#)).

Fig 3: Inference of mechanisms across levels. *Inferring the activity of cellular processes at different levels ranging from intercellular interactions via secreted ligands to regulation of gene expression via transcription factors.*

Inferring the Activity of Functional Modules

Considerable effort has been put into curating gene sets comprising the constituents of various functional modules, including metabolic processes (e.g. glycolysis, oxidative phosphorylation), stress responses (e.g. hypoxia, unfolded protein response), or immune functions (e.g. phagocytosis, TCR signaling, exhaustion, anergy), exemplified by resources like GO ²⁵, KEGG ²⁶, Reactome ²⁷, or MSigDB ²⁸. Enrichment methods ^{29,30} such as gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) ²⁸ can be combined with these gene sets to infer the activity of the corresponding functional modules. Importantly, inferring the status of a module using the mRNA expression of its protein constituents only works if there is a strong correlation between the mRNA levels and the activity of encoded proteins.

Inference of Transcription Factor Activity

TFs are crucial for cell differentiation ³¹, and play a key role as mediators of acute responses to pathogens and cytokines via various pathways, such as Toll-like receptor signaling (NF- κ B and IRFs) ³². To understand the diversity of immune cell types and mechanisms modulating their response, it is therefore indispensable to systematically infer which TFs are active within a given cell type in a specific context ³³.

Often researchers implicitly assume that the mRNA levels of a TF correspond to its activity, yet this assumption is generally inaccurate as many TFs can be regulated at the post-transcriptional level ³². Leveraging knowledge about the target genes of TFs available in databases ^{16,34–36}, we can get better TF activity estimates by considering instead the expression of target genes ³⁰. These databases are based on genome-wide assays of TF binding such as chromatin immunoprecipitation sequencing (ChIP-seq); in-silico prediction of TF binding based on TF motifs and genomic sequences; manual curation of literature or text-mining; and/or co-expression of TFs and target genes derived from RNA-seq.

When deciding which GRN database to use, it is important to consider the trade-off between the number of TFs covered and the accuracy of the TF-gene interactions. Benchmarks based on TF perturbation experiments have shown that manually curated networks are most accurate, followed by networks based on genome-wide TF binding assays, while networks inferred from *in silico* prediction of TF binding sites or RNA co-expression are less accurate but provide much higher TF coverage ^{16,37}.

Inference of Context-Specific Gene Regulatory Networks

GRN databases often pool evidence from many different tissues or cell types, yielding generalistic networks which are not specific to any context. However, TF-gene interactions depend on many context-specific factors such as the presence of cofactors, DNA methylation, and chromatin accessibility ³⁸. To address this challenge, many algorithms have been developed that harness the resolution of single-cell transcriptomics, i.e. the ability to measure co-variation of gene

expression across thousands of cells, to infer cell type or state-specific GRNs³⁹. Yet, benchmarks based on both simulated and experimental data have shown that the accuracy of algorithms which are only based on scRNA-seq is only marginally better than random^{37,40,41}.

Since recently, gene expression and chromatin accessibility can be measured in single cells at the same time allowing to quantify not only co-expression, but also the activity of cis-regulatory elements such as promoters and enhancers⁷. Combining such technologies with prior knowledge about TF binding motifs, multiple new algorithms have been developed to infer more accurate GRNs by considering both co-expression of TFs and target genes as well as the presence of putative TF binding sites in active cis-regulatory elements⁴². Thereby, these algorithms can infer interactions between cis-regulatory elements either by modeling enhancer-promoter interactions or implicitly by considering interactions between enhancers when they regulate the same gene. The resulting context-specific GRNs can be used to answer a variety of questions (see [Table 1](#))⁴².

The power of such approaches was recently illustrated by Wayman and colleagues who used context-specific GRNs to characterize the splenic CD4⁺ memory T cell (CD4⁺TM) populations in young and old mice: Motivated by their previous study which linked a CD4⁺TM population (IL-10 expression T follicular helper cell [Tfh10]) to age-associated immune dysfunction, the researchers set out to comprehensively characterize the CD4⁺TM compartment using scRNA- and scATAC-seq. The researchers identified several cell states whose abundance changes with age, including Tfh10 as well as conventional regulatory and central memory T cells. Using gene sets for functional characterization, they also found many cell state-specific deregulated functional modules. To explore the mechanisms underlying these aging dynamics, the researchers inferred cell state-specific GRNs, and used them to compute which TFs exhibit age-dependent differential activity in each cell state. In Tfh10, they found that Stat3 activity increases with age which might underlie the observed reduction in interferon- γ response, while higher activity of Zbtb7a and Zfp143 might underlie the upregulation of anti-apoptotic pathways⁴³.

Even though the inference of context-specific GRNs opens many exciting research avenues, one must be aware that the current algorithms ignore many important processes including post-transcriptional processes affecting the activity of TFs, such as splicing, chemical modifications, translocation into the nucleus as well as TF crosstalk⁴⁴ (Fig. 4). Additionally, many other regulatory components such as non-coding RNAs, the 3D chromatin structure, and very distant cis-regulatory elements are not considered in the current models⁴². Furthermore, to date, there is no independent benchmark comparing recent GRN inference algorithms, which is anyway challenging due to the limited ground truth data, so that one cannot recommend one approach over another⁴². Apart from the algorithm, the choice of TF motif database can have a substantial impact on the resulting GRNs because the databases have varying coverage of TFs. The most comprehensive database is the SCENIC+ motif collection, created by pooling information from 29 other databases⁴⁵. Due to the aforementioned lack of benchmarks, we advise to validate the plausibility of the inferred networks by comparing with available experimental data for the context of interest and by checking whether known regulators have been recovered.

Fig 4: The limitations of current single-cell technologies. *Whereas some molecules and processes can be quantified comprehensively at the single-cell level, others are currently*

beyond our technical capabilities. Our measuring capabilities ultimately determine which assumptions we have to make when modeling biological processes. PTMs, posttranslational modifications. Abbreviations: transcription factor (TF), post-translational modification (PTM).

Inference of Intracellular Signaling Activity

Signaling cascades integrate external stimuli with the internal state of the cell to generate appropriate cellular responses ⁴⁶, which are often connected to gene regulation via transcription factors ⁴⁷. These cascades are commonly summarized as canonical signaling pathways, such as the JAK-STAT pathway ²⁷. Quantifying the activity of signaling pathways is challenging, since the information is frequently mediated via short-lived post-translational modifications (PTMs) ⁴⁸ that are difficult to measure at scale - especially at the single-cell level ⁴⁹. To circumvent these limitations, we can instead use transcriptome data to quantify the activity of signaling pathways by considering the expression of genes that are regulated by a given pathway ⁵⁰, similar to the inference of TF activity. To that end, large numbers of published perturbation experiments have been compiled to derive gene expression signatures for canonical signaling pathways ^{17,51} and cytokines ⁵².

Given that signaling pathways do not operate in isolation, accurate descriptions of how signals are propagated require analyzing the signaling network as a whole, as done by methods that combine prior knowledge of protein-protein interaction networks with omics data ⁵³. These network-based approaches are typically computationally more expensive than signature-based methods. Both types of approaches to infer signaling activity are affected by research bias (see [Box 5](#)): Some proteins are much more studied than others, leading to systematic biases in the annotated interactions which network-based approaches rely on ⁵³, while signature-based approaches rely on perturbation data from a limited set of contexts, comprising mostly cancer cell lines ¹⁷.

Intercellular Processes

The coordination of immune cells is essential for an effective response to pathogens. Such coordination is achieved through a complex network of intercellular interactions across diverse cell types, regulated by a variety of signaling molecules⁵. To systematically infer cell-cell communication (CCC) events from single-cell transcriptomics, we can utilize prior knowledge about ligand-receptor and receptor-receptor complexes. These data are usually derived from experimental methods like co-immunoprecipitation and proximity-based labeling in combination with proteomics or X-ray crystallography¹⁸.

Inference of Intercellular Signaling from Dissociated Single-Cell Data

Recently, many approaches have emerged to infer CCC by combining single-cell transcriptomics with prior knowledge¹⁸. These can be generally separated into two categories: the most commonly used type of CCC approaches are the so-called ligand-receptor inference methods^{18,54}. These methods are based on databases that catalog ligand-receptor or receptor-receptor complexes, which are used to infer interactions between cell types by quantifying the co-expression of cognate ligand-receptor or receptor-receptor pairs^{18,54}. Such a method has been used to systematically investigate the maternal-fetal interface in humans, revealing many immunomodulatory processes that might restrain maternal immune responses, including the expression of checkpoint inhibitors by decidual natural killer cells (TIGIT, KLRB1) and CD8⁺ T cells (PD-1) as well as the expression of anti-inflammatory cytokines by decidual macrophages (IL-10) and decidual natural killer cells (SPINK2, ANXA1)⁵⁵.

The second common variant of CCC approaches additionally models intracellular signaling as a response of cell-cell interactions¹⁸. A common strategy is to use the expression of putative target genes of ligands to estimate CCC events, similarly to the inference of TF or pathway activities^{52,56}. To derive target genes for ligands, prior knowledge of ligand-receptor interactions, signaling pathways, and TF-gene interactions can be combined to construct a network connecting ligands to genes⁵⁶. Another approach is to use transcriptome perturbation datasets to derive

gene expression signatures for ligands, which has recently been done to infer signatures for cytokines, chemokines, and growth factors ⁵². This resource has been used to construct a statistical model that enables researchers to quantify how different genes modulate the negative effect of immunosuppressive cytokines (TGF- β 1, TRAIL, PGE2) on T cell function in solid cancers. This analysis led to the identification of FIBP as a novel regulator of T cell resilience. Across several tumor types, higher FIBP expression in T cells was strongly associated with an enhanced effect of immunosuppressive cytokines on T cell function. To further investigate these associations, the researchers used human cell lines and mouse models, showing that CD8⁺ T with FIBP deficiency have increased antitumor efficacy ⁵⁷.

Most methods infer interactions that occur between groups of cells (e.g. cell types). Therefore, the obtained results are influenced by the granularity of the annotation and might miss interactions specific to rare cell states ⁵⁸. Addressing this issue, novel tools have emerged that infer intercellular communication at the single-cell level ^{58,59}. Comparing scRNA-seq data of leprosy granulomas from patients with disseminated lepromatous leprosy to patients undergoing a reversal reaction, Wilk et al. showed how previously reported CCC events underlying reversal reaction are not recovered using state-of-the-art methods that work at the cluster level. In contrast, using their single-cell based workflow, the authors successfully identified an interaction of cytotoxic (CRTAM⁺) CD4⁺ T cells with myeloid cells via interferon- γ which is thought to lower pathogen burden in reversal reactions by upregulating inflammatory mediators (e.g. L1B, CCL3 and TNF) ⁵⁸.

While these examples illustrate the potential power of communication inference from dissociated single-cell data, there are many things commonly omitted: Cells do not only communicate via protein ligands, but also via mechanical or electric signals, extracellular vesicles, and metabolites ^{60,61} - which are especially important in host-microbiome ⁶² and immune cell interactions ⁶³. First approaches have been developed to model metabolite-mediated CCC from transcriptomics data ⁶⁴⁻⁶⁷, but the accuracy of these methods remains to be established. Furthermore, the models we use to infer protein-mediated communication are limited in many ways: Ligand-receptor methods ignore secretion and diffusion processes, and assume a

high correlation of mRNA levels and activity of the encoded proteins (Fig. 4). In contrast, methods that model the downstream effects of CCC events suffer from biases in our prior knowledge on protein-protein interaction networks or the generalistic nature of gene expression signatures derived from many different contexts (see Box 5). Addressing the latter problem, cell type-specific signatures have recently been generated for more than 80 cytokines using scRNA-seq to profile murine immune cells in lymph nodes after cytokine injection, revealing highly specific responses in many immune cell types⁶⁸.

Given that direct measurement of CCC events in a high-throughput manner is challenging, existing benchmarks rely on indirect information such as spatial information or the expression of putative target genes of ligands to evaluate the plausibility of inferred interactions^{54,69}. These benchmarks have shown that most ligand-receptor methods seem to perform better than random^{54,69}, and that the inferred predictions are very sensitive to the choice of ligand-receptor resource and statistical model, resulting in discordant predictions across methods⁵⁴.

Considering the absence of ground truth to benchmark methods, it is hard to determine which tool works better. We strongly suggest checking whether there is literature support for some of the highly-scored interactions as curation practices vary between ligand-receptor resources⁵⁴. Additionally, two main strategies have emerged to reduce the large number of potential interactions that we elaborate below: (1) prioritize CCC events that exhibit large variation between conditions^{65,70,71}; (2) prioritize CCC events where the corresponding cell groups and ligand-receptor complexes co-localize *in situ*.

Inference of Intercellular Signaling from Cross-Condition Data

Two main strategies have emerged to extract deregulated CCC events across conditions, related to recently developed methods that identify coordinated gene expression programs across cell types and samples (Box 3). The first class of methods uses differential gene expression analysis^{65,70} to prioritize ligand-receptor complexes whose expression robustly changes between conditions. The second class of methods uses higher-order factorization approaches^{65,71} which enables the

identification of coordinated CCC events involving multiple cell types and ligand-receptor complexes. One such approach ⁷¹ was used to analyze bronchoalveolar lavage fluid samples from healthy individuals and COVID-19 patients, leading to the identification of CCC patterns across patients that were strongly associated with disease severity. Consistent with previous reports ⁷², the analysis identified deregulated crosstalk between epithelial cells and a broad array of immune cells, including B and T cells as well as macrophages and dendritic cells.

Inference of Intercellular Signaling from Spatially Resolved Data

Intercellular communication, except for endocrine signaling, depends on spatial proximity. Thus, the emergence of diverse spatial (multi)-omics technologies ^{19,20} offers a promising avenue to study CCC. Given the current technological trade-off between spatial resolution and transcriptome coverage, most technologies with single-cell resolution only measure tens to hundreds of markers, whereas whole transcriptome measurements are limited to spots containing several cells ^{19,20}. On the one hand, this dilemma led to the development of tools that use low-plexity, high-resolution spatial data to infer intercellular interactions by quantifying the co-localization of cell groups without considering which ligands or receptors might underlie those interactions (**Box 4**) ⁷³. On the other hand, tools were developed to identify CCC events from high-plexity, low-resolution spatial data by first identifying the main cell type in a given spot, or by working with cell type fractions per spot ⁷⁴. Such spatial information was initially used to extend classical ligand-receptor methods by constraining the inferred interactions to cell type pairs that co-localize ^{75,76}. Akin to network-based methods, more recent methods additionally consider prior knowledge networks that connect receptors to TFs and their target genes. ^{65,77} Furthermore, spatial data not only allow us to infer which cell types co-localize, but also to directly quantify where in the tissue ligands and receptors are co-expressed ^{59,65,78,79}.

We recently used spatially constrained ligand-receptor inference to gain insights into the CCC events of cell types contributing to mucosal healing. Initially applying ligand-receptor methods to assess interactions between intestinal stromal

and epithelial cell clusters from dissociated scRNA-seq datasets yielded no specific interactions related to the repair process. However, additional spatial transcriptomics datasets allowed us to identify the clusters of stromal and epithelial cells which are localized in healing areas, leading to the identification interactions crucial for tissue remodeling. This strategy revealed that tissue remodeling appears to be enhanced in the absence of B cells ⁸⁰.

Given the added value of spatial data, we generally recommend using such technologies to study CCC in tissues. To reduce the cost, one can for example combine transcriptome data from dissociated single cells with data from low-plexity spatial technologies, e.g. iterative fluorescent imaging ^{19,20}, which still allows for quantification of cell type co-localization.

Yet, when dealing with spatial data we must be aware of the current limitations. For example, segmentation of imaging data can be extremely difficult if cells have intricate shapes. Furthermore, 2D images of tissues might bias our estimation of CCC: One recent study found that tertiary lymphoid structures in colorectal cancer that seemed to be detached in 2D were often interconnected when imaged using 3D technology ⁸¹.

Conclusions

To summarize, we have reviewed approaches that integrate single-cell and spatial (multi)-omics data with existing biological knowledge to generate more informative representations of single cells, cell types, and tissues ([Fig. 2](#)), allowing for example the identification of deregulated transcription factors or alterations in intra- or intercellular signaling. These insights will ultimately help us to construct detailed dynamic mechanistic models ⁶ for these processes and devise effective therapeutic strategies to enhance disease treatment.

The current algorithms used to generate more interpretable representations are limited by biases in our existing biological knowledge ([Box 5](#)) as well as our limited ability to measure molecules ([Fig. 4](#)) due to technological trade-offs among: 1) Multiplicity - number of distinct molecules we can quantify simultaneously; 2) Location - whether we can measure the position within a tissue; 3) Dynamics -

whether we can measure over a time-course. For instance, most transcriptome- or proteome-wide assays are intrinsically destructive and thus offer only static snapshots, whereas classic fluorescent protein tagging is applicable to time- and spatially resolved measurements for a limited subset of proteins. Integrating these different types of measurement using computational models relies on the assumption that measurements in one sample, such as the localization of a GFP-tagged protein at the plasma membrane, holds true in another sample. More generally, to model any kind of intra- and intercellular processes, we must make numerous assumptions as described throughout the manuscript. Therefore, we must be mindful that the conclusions drawn from computational models applied to omics data are hypotheses that need to be studied in more detail by orthogonal experimental approaches.

Future Perspectives

Emerging methodological and technological developments are paving the way for building ever more accurate computational models of biological processes, consequently deepening our understanding of the immune system.

Gaps and biases in our prior knowledge will be reduced by advances in experimental technologies. For example, CRISPR screens have been combined with high-content read-outs like scRNA-seq or multiplexed imaging, allowing detailed assessment of single gene perturbations in a high-throughput manner⁸². Functional proteomics technologies such as crosslinking mass spectrometry or thermal proteome profiling are promising to reveal protein interactions for neglected proteins⁸³. Immunopeptidomics enable the identification of thousands of peptides with the capacity to bind human leukocyte antigen class II (HLA-II) on antigen-presenting cells, representing a powerful technology for antigen discovery⁸⁴.

Complementary orthogonal approaches, our measurement capabilities at the single-cell level are rapidly improving. While the transcriptome has been the focus for many years, it is now becoming increasingly feasible to measure the proteome at single-cell resolution⁸⁵, while also preserving spatial context⁸⁶. In line, there has been tremendous progress in spatial metabolomics, with some technologies being

able to measure more than 100 metabolites in single cells ⁸⁷, and other technologies pioneering the co-profiling of metabolites and the transcriptome ⁸⁸. We anticipate that combining these technological advancements with recent progress in inferring small molecule-mediated CCC from transcriptomic data ⁶⁴⁻⁶⁷ will soon enable the reliable inference of such communication events. More generally, our understanding of how cell-cell interactions and spatial organization shape cellular phenotypes is set to improve given the emerging array of spatial multi-omics technologies ^{19,20}. Recently published technologies include the co-profiling of the transcriptome together with chromatin accessibility ⁸⁹, histone modifications ⁹⁰, adaptive immune receptor sequences ⁹¹, metabolites ⁸⁸, surface proteins ⁹², and microbiome taxa ^{93,94}. Such technologies hold the promise for identifying metabolite-mediated immune cell-microbiome interaction. Besides spatial profiling, there are multiple emerging technologies poised to improve our understanding of CCC. One study recently reported how hydrogel nanovials could be used to simultaneously profile the transcriptome and the secretion of VEGF-A ⁹⁵. Other emerging technologies employ synthetic pathways ⁹⁶ or engineered viral systems ⁹⁷ to trace cell-cell contact histories.

As previously mentioned, it is crucial to not only consider what we can measure and at what resolution but also whether we can track quantities over time to study the dynamics of biological processes. Here, the combination of multiphoton intravital microscopy followed by static 3D immunofluorescence microscopy has been proposed as a way to measure the dynamics of immune cells while also capturing some aspects of the phenotypic diversity ⁹⁸. Integrating the multiplexed immunofluorescence data with scRNA-seq to impute the full transcriptome, one could enhance the power of that approach even further ⁷⁴. Additionally, a recent study pioneered the use of fluidic force microscopy to extract RNA from living cells which enables time-resolved transcriptome-wide measurements *in vitro* ⁹⁹. The authors demonstrated the value of their technology by measuring the transcriptome of individual macrophages before and after stimulation with lipopolysaccharide, revealing key determinants of the response heterogeneity.

Throughout the review we have described that gene expression signatures and other gene sets are limited based on the tissues and cell types they have been derived from. To address the generalistic nature of gene sets, new computational approaches are emerging that leverage the large variability of single-cell gene expression profiles to modify gene sets such that they better explain the observed variance in specific contexts ¹⁰⁰⁻¹⁰². This concept was used in the analysis of non-metastatic breast cancer samples to refine the gene set indicating tumor reactive T cells ¹⁰⁰, helping to identify a population of tumor-reactive CD8⁺ T cells that was highly enriched patients responding to anti-PD-1 treatment.

Emerging modeling paradigms inspired by the success of large language models (e.g. GPT-4 ¹⁰³) can significantly impact biological research. Deep learning models that are trained on millions of scRNA-seq profiles can learn intricate relationships between genes, surpassing the capabilities of classical co-expression analysis ^{104,105}. These models can be fine-tuned for many tasks ranging from predicting the effect of unseen drug or genetic perturbation to cell annotation, although their ability to outperform task-specific models has yet to be proven.

In summary, the application of computational methods that integrate single-cell and spatial multi-omics with existing biological knowledge is valuable in deciphering which cells and molecules of the immune system and which interactions underlie different functional outcomes. Thereby, these approaches help to define a scaffold from which more refined computational models can be build ⁶, in particular dynamic quantitative models (e.g. based on differential equations and agent based modeling), which enable the simulation of unobserved scenarios, and consequently the generation of specific testable hypotheses ^{106,107}.

Table 1: Questions that can be addressed using GRNs

Description	Publication Example
<p>TF activity inference: GRNs can be used to infer TF activity based on the expression of their target genes. This can also be done in spatial transcriptomics datasets to see how the cellular neighborhood shapes TF activity ⁴⁵.</p>	<p>Used to identify TFs that have age-dependent differential activity in CD4⁺ T cells which might underlie age-associated immune dysfunction in the spleen ⁴³.</p>
<p>Identification of differential TF-gene edges: Comparing the edges of GRNs allows for assessing the rewiring of TF-gene connections in different cell types and/or conditions. Alternatively, one can identify the TFs that drive different cell states by identifying the TFs that are strongly connected to differentially expressed genes between those cell states.</p>	<p>Used to identify TFs that might underlie the remission-associated expansion of precursor exhausted T cells in response to immunotherapy treatment in chronic myelogenous leukemia ¹⁰⁸</p>
<p>Identification of master regulators: Network centrality measures such as the eigenvector centrality can be used to identify the most important TFs in a given network.</p>	<p>Used to identify potential master regulators of myofibroblast differentiation in human myocardial infarction ¹⁰⁹</p>
<p>Identification of gene modules: Graph-based clustering (e.g. Louvain clustering) can be used to identify modules of co-regulated genes.</p>	<p>Used to characterize a GRN of naive macrophages, yielding gene modules underlying the potential to polarize into M1 or M2 states ¹¹⁰.</p>
<p>In-silico perturbation: Some GRN inference tools additionally offer methods to simulate the effects of TF expression changes on differentiation dynamics ^{45,111}.</p>	<p>Used to characterize a cluster of hematopoietic stem cells associated with severe sepsis outcomes, showing that the cluster is driven by CEBPB and STAT3 which are known drivers of emergency granulopoiesis ¹¹².</p>
<p>Interpretation of genomic variants: Many disease-associated genetic variants are in non-coding regions. GRN inference could help to interpret</p>	<p>Cell state-specific macrophage GRNs were used to pinpoint the particular cell state in which fine-mapped GWAS</p>

those variants by linking non-coding regions to the genes they might regulate and to cell states/types in which they are active.

variants associated with autoimmune disease might play a role ¹¹⁰.

Box 1: Using single-cell repertoire analysis to learn about lymphocyte biology

Through DNA rearrangement, B and T cells acquire unique antigen receptors. Unlike bulk sequencing of populations isolated based on a few dozen surface markers, paired single-cell sequencing of antigen receptor sequences and the transcriptome [scV(D)J-seq]¹¹³ allows us to associate single receptor sequences with phenotypic information in an unbiased way^{114,115}. This technology can be combined with profiling of antigen specificities using DNA-barcoded pMHC tetramers¹¹⁶. scV(D)J-seq greatly improves our ability to investigate repertoire dynamics upon treatment or disease. We can ask how repertoire features such as diversity, V(D)J usage, or amino acid motifs¹¹⁷ change within the same or different cell types/states across conditions¹¹⁸. We can also group cells based on their antigen receptor sequence similarity^{119,120} or based on whether their clonotype expanded or contracted, and analyze these groups with much higher molecular resolution¹²¹.

scV(D)J-seq is not only useful to illuminate disease or treatment responses but it also provides valuable insights into lymphocyte development, since the antigen receptor sequence can be used to trace clonal relationships, while the transcriptome can be used to infer differentiation states. This approach recently provided support for the lineage model of B1 origination in humans, as researchers found that some pre-pro B and B1 cells but not pro- or pre-B cells express nonproductive T cell receptor β chains. This supports the hypothesis that B1 cells differentiate from distinct fetal pre-pro B cells, bypassing the pre- and pro-B cell stages. This could explain why B1 cells are often self-reactive since they evade the pre-BCR selection step¹²².

Apart from enabling a detailed annotation of lymphocytes, the transcriptome can also be directly associated with antigen receptor sequences to learn more fine-grained dependencies between functional characteristics and the receptor sequence¹²³⁻¹²⁶. In a proof of principle, Zhang et al. used their model to compare the association between TCR sequences and gene expression of CD8⁺ T cells in control and tumor samples, finding that the association is generally reduced in cancer contexts. This reduction likely reflects the elevated presence of signaling molecules in the tumor microenvironment which influences gene expression independently

of the TCR sequence, resulting in similar gene expression patterns across different T cell clones ¹²³.

Similar to the analysis of transcriptome data, prior knowledge is valuable when analyzing scV(D)J-seq, in particular to infer information on the epitope specificity from antigen receptor sequences. For example, databases cataloging TCR-pMHC complexes, help us in at least three ways: (1) Available 3D structures help us to determine which amino acids in the TCR sequence are most important for binding ¹¹⁹; (2) Databases cataloging TCR-pMHC complexes can be queried to find putative epitope for a given TCR sequence ¹²⁷; (3) The same databases can be used to train ML models to predict whether a given TCR binds a known epitope ¹²⁸.

Box 2: Annotating cells into biologically meaningful groups

A common step in single-cell omics is the annotation of measured cells into groups corresponding to known cell types. This process has been typically done by making use of known marker genes, carried out in a discordant manner by independent groups ¹²⁹. Yet, when studying different cell types or states, we - as a research community - have to make sure that we talk about the same entity when using a certain label. This is especially important since the increasing resolution of single-cell technologies has revealed a large variability of functional phenotypes even within the same cell type. To harmonize annotations, preliminary work proposes the use of cell ontologies ¹²⁹. Complementary, different algorithms have been proposed to automatically annotate single-cell data ^{10,130-132} based on the plethora of high-quality datasets which have been annotated by experts ^{9,11}.

Box 3: Identification of multicellular programs from cross-condition scRNA-seq datasets

Assuming that cellular coordination creates recurring gene expression patterns, novel algorithms have been developed that leverage the increasing availability of large, cross-condition single-cell datasets to identify co-varying gene programs in multiple cell types ¹³³⁻¹³⁵. These gene expression programs involving multiple cell types are often called multicellular programs. For example, applying such an

approach to scRNA-seq samples from colonoscopies of healthy individuals and ulcerative colitis patients led to the identification of a multicellular program whose activity is strongly associated with ulcerative colitis. This program involved not only immune cells (macrophages, T cells) but also two intestinal epithelial cell types. While the epithelial programs were enriched in markers for leukocyte migration, the macrophage program was characterized by upregulation of genes associated with leukocyte and lymphocyte activation, and the T cell program by genes associated with effector T cell function.¹³³ In summary, these approaches provide an opportunity to capture the interplay between different cell types.

Box 4: Cell-cell interactions from spatial data without relying on prior knowledge

Many spatial profiling technologies, especially those with high resolution, are limited in the number of markers that can be measured. To allow for the integration with existing knowledge and other data modalities, most probes or antibodies are usually chosen to identify cell types, limiting the systems-level inference of CCC. By assuming that interacting cell types co-localize more often than expected by chance, some methods infer pairwise cell-cell interactions using only the spatial distribution of cell types^{75,136–138}. Other methods go beyond pairwise interactions and aim to identify niches or microenvironments that are characterized by certain cell type compositions^{75,139–141}. Such approaches have been used to analyze how cellular interactions define the response to immunotherapy in triple negative breast cancer patients, revealing for instance that an increased co-localization of CD20⁺ B cells and GZMB⁺ CD8⁺ T cells with tumor cells is highly associated with response to immune checkpoint blockade¹⁴².

If some of the measured markers provide functional information, then considering solely cell type labels disregards information that could be used to infer cell-cell interactions. Specifically, one can assume that interactions between cells lead to coordinated changes in gene expression. Based on this assumption, machine learning models have been developed that model gene expression based on features of the spatial neighborhood, which allows for the inference of cell-cell interactions

143–145.

Box 5: Limitations of prior biological knowledge

Research bias: Some genes (e.g. P53) and some contexts (e.g. common cancer types) receive disproportionate attention ^{47,53,83}, to the point that more than 90% of life science literature pertaining to genes and their functions is focused on less than 5,000 proteins ¹⁴⁶. This bias can arise from factors ranging from funding policies to inherent challenges in investigating certain biological processes. Consequently, there is a higher likelihood of rediscovering well-studied elements, potentially hindering the discovery of novel immunological mechanisms. Even for well-studied groups of proteins such as TFs there is a strong research bias ^{47,147}, as more than 10% of all human TFs currently lack a binding motif ¹⁴⁷.

Lack of context-specificity: Pathway annotations and gene expression signatures are often derived from many different tissues, cell types, and disease contexts. Thus, the annotation of pathways or expression signatures found in databases often do not reflect the conditions at hand. The same signal (e.g. IL-6 signaling) can have different responses in target cells ^{46,56,68} depending on which receptor subunits are expressed ^{148,149}, which chromatin regions are accessible, and whether certain signaling and transcriptional regulators are present. For example, IL-6 signaling during naïve CD4⁺ T cell activation may result in IL17-producing T cells (Th17) or follicular helper T cells (Tfh) differentiation depending on the presence or absence of TGF- β ¹⁵⁰.

Quantity-quality trade-off: There is often a trade-off between coverage and quality when it comes to prior knowledge as demonstrated by the comparison of manually curated GRNs with networks that are based on *in silico* prediction of TF binding sites or RNA co-expression ¹⁶.

Acknowledgements

P.S.L.S. has received funding from the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft under grant agreement SPP 2395. D.D. is supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (860329 Marie-Curie ITN "STRATEGY-CKD").

We thank Ricardo Omar Ramirez Flores, Pau Badia i Mompel, Jovan Tanevski, Leonie Küchenhoff, Martin Garrido-Rodriguez, Chang Lu, and Katharina Mikulik for the helpful discussions.

Author Contributions

P.S.L.S., D.D., and J.S.R. developed the concept based on starting ideas from J.S.R. P.S.L.S. designed the figures. P.S.L.S., with assistance from D.D., wrote the original draft, with the supervision of J.S.R. E.J.V. contributed immunological expertise. All authors reviewed and edited the manuscript.

Conflict of Interests

J.S.R. reports funding from GSK, Pfizer and Sanofi and fees/honoraria from Traverre Therapeutics, Stadapharm, Astex, Pfizer, Owkin and Grunenthal. E.J.V. has received research grants from F. Hoffmann-La Roche. All other authors declare no competing interests.

References

1. Arunachalam, P. S. *et al.* Systems biological assessment of immunity to mild versus severe COVID-19 infection in humans. *Science* **369**, 1210–1220 (2020).
2. Shen-Orr, S. S. & Furman, D. Variability in the immune system: of vaccine responses and immune states. *Curr. Opin. Immunol.* **25**, 542–547 (2013).
3. Yofe, I., Dahan, R. & Amit, I. Single-cell genomic approaches for developing the next generation of immunotherapies. *Nat. Med.* **26**, 171–177 (2020).
4. Banchereau, R., Cepika, A.-M. & Pascual, V. Systems approaches to human autoimmune diseases. *Curr. Opin. Immunol.* **25**, 598–605 (2013).
5. Davis, M. M., Tato, C. M. & Furman, D. Systems immunology: just getting started. *Nat. Immunol.* **18**, 725–732 (2017).
6. Germain, R. N., Meier-Schellersheim, M., Nita-Lazar, A. & Fraser, I. D. C. Systems biology in immunology: a computational modeling perspective. *Annu. Rev. Immunol.* **29**, 527–585 (2011).
7. Ma, S. *et al.* Chromatin Potential Identified by Shared Single-Cell Profiling of RNA and Chromatin. *Cell* **183**, 1103–1116.e20 (2020).

This work pioneered paired sequencing of chromatin accessibility and transcriptome in single cells (SHARE-seq).
8. Ståhl, P. L. *et al.* Visualization and analysis of gene expression in tissue sections by spatial transcriptomics. *Science* **353**, 78–82 (2016).

This work pioneered spatially-resolved transcriptomics.

9. Regev, A. *et al.* The human cell atlas. *eLife* **6**, (2017). doi: 10.7554/eLife.27041
10. Domínguez Conde, C. *et al.* Cross-tissue immune cell analysis reveals tissue-specific features in humans. *Science* **376**, eabl5197 (2022).
11. HuBMAP Consortium. The human body at cellular resolution: the NIH Human Biomolecular Atlas Program. *Nature* **574**, 187–192 (2019).
12. Martin, F. J. *et al.* Ensembl 2023. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **51**, D933–D941 (2023).
13. UniProt Consortium. Uniprot: the universal protein knowledgebase in 2023. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **51**, D523–D531 (2023).
14. Türei, D. *et al.* Integrated intra- and intercellular signaling knowledge for multicellular omics analysis. *Mol. Syst. Biol.* **17**, (2021). doi: 10.15252/msb.20209923

This work introduces a comprehensive meta-resource that collects data from over a hundred databases, including for example protein interaction networks, ligand-receptor annotations, and protein complex information.

15. Szklarczyk, D. *et al.* STITCH 5: augmenting protein-chemical interaction networks with tissue and affinity data. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **44**, D380-4 (2016).
16. Garcia-Alonso, L., Holland, C. H., Ibrahim, M. M., Turei, D. & Saez-Rodriguez, J. Benchmark and integration of resources for the estimation of human transcription factor activities. *Genome Res.* **29**, 1363–1375 (2019).

17. Schubert, M. *et al.* Perturbation-response genes reveal signaling footprints in cancer gene expression. *Nat. Commun.* **9**, 20 (2018).
18. Armingol, E., Officer, A., Harismendy, O. & Lewis, N. E. Deciphering cell-cell interactions and communication from gene expression. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* **22**, 71–88 (2021).
19. Vandereyken, K., Sifrim, A., Thienpont, B. & Voet, T. Methods and applications for single-cell and spatial multi-omics. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* **24**, 494–515 (2023).
20. Baysoy, A., Bai, Z., Satija, R. & Fan, R. The technological landscape and applications of single-cell multi-omics. *Nat. Rev. Mol. Cell Biol.* **24**, 695–713 (2023).
21. Bonaguro, L. *et al.* A guide to systems-level immunomics. *Nat. Immunol.* **23**, 1412–1423 (2022).
22. Stuart, T. *et al.* Comprehensive Integration of Single-Cell Data. *Cell* **177**, 1888–1902.e21 (2019).
23. Heumos, L. *et al.* Best practices for single-cell analysis across modalities. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* **24**, 550–572 (2023).
24. Amezquita, R. A. *et al.* Orchestrating single-cell analysis with Bioconductor. *Nat. Methods* **17**, 137–145 (2020).
25. Gene Ontology Consortium *et al.* The Gene Ontology knowledgebase in 2023. *Genetics* **224**, (2023). doi: 10.1093/genetics/iyad031

26. Kanehisa, M., Furumichi, M., Sato, Y., Kawashima, M. & Ishiguro-Watanabe, M. KEGG for taxonomy-based analysis of pathways and genomes. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **51**, D587–D592 (2023).
27. Gillespie, M. *et al.* The reactome pathway knowledgebase 2022. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **50**, D687–D692 (2022).
28. Subramanian, A. *et al.* Gene set enrichment analysis: a knowledge-based approach for interpreting genome-wide expression profiles. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* **102**, 15545–15550 (2005).
29. Våremo, L., Nielsen, J. & Nookaew, I. Enriching the gene set analysis of genome-wide data by incorporating directionality of gene expression and combining statistical hypotheses and methods. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **41**, 4378–4391 (2013).
30. Badia-I-Mompel, P. *et al.* decoupleR: ensemble of computational methods to infer biological activities from omics data. *Bioinformatics Advances* **2**, vbac016 (2022).
31. Hosokawa, H. & Rothenberg, E. V. How transcription factors drive choice of the T cell fate. *Nat. Rev. Immunol.* **21**, 162–176 (2021).
32. Kawasaki, T. & Kawai, T. Toll-like receptor signaling pathways. *Front. Immunol.* **5**, 461 (2014).
33. Saini, A., Ghoneim, H. E., Lio, C.-W. J., Collins, P. L. & Oltz, E. M. Gene regulatory circuits in innate and adaptive immune cells. *Annu. Rev. Immunol.* **40**, 387–411 (2022).

34. Liu, Z.-P., Wu, C., Miao, H. & Wu, H. RegNetwork: an integrated database of transcriptional and post-transcriptional regulatory networks in human and mouse. *Database (Oxford)* **2015**, (2015). doi: 10.1093/database/bav095
35. Keenan, A. B. *et al.* ChEA3: transcription factor enrichment analysis by orthogonal omics integration. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **47**, W212–W224 (2019).
36. Müller-Dott, S. *et al.* Expanding the coverage of regulons from high-confidence prior knowledge for accurate estimation of transcription factor activities. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **51**, 10934–10949 (2023).
37. Holland, C. H. *et al.* Robustness and applicability of transcription factor and pathway analysis tools on single-cell RNA-seq data. *Genome Biol.* **21**, 36 (2020).
38. Zeitlinger, J. Seven myths of how transcription factors read the cis-regulatory code. *Current Opinion in Systems Biology* **23**, 22–31 (2020).
39. Fiers, M. W. E. J. *et al.* Mapping gene regulatory networks from single-cell omics data. *Brief. Funct. Genomics* **17**, 246–254 (2018).
40. Chen, S. & Mar, J. C. Evaluating methods of inferring gene regulatory networks highlights their lack of performance for single cell gene expression data. *BMC Bioinformatics* **19**, 232 (2018).
41. Pratapa, A., Jalihal, A. P., Law, J. N., Bharadwaj, A. & Murali, T. M. Benchmarking algorithms for gene regulatory network inference from single-cell transcriptomic data. *Nat. Methods* **17**, 147–154 (2020).

42. Badia-I-Mompel, P. *et al.* Gene regulatory network inference in the era of single-cell multi-omics. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* **24**, 739–754 (2023).
43. Wayman, J. A. *et al.* An atlas of gene regulatory networks for memory CD4 + T cells in youth and old age. *BioRxiv* (2023) doi:10.1101/2023.03.07.531590.
44. Chowdhary, K. & Benoist, C. A variegated model of transcription factor function in the immune system. *Trends Immunol.* **44**, 530–541 (2023).
45. Bravo González-Blas, C. *et al.* SCENIC+: single-cell multiomic inference of enhancers and gene regulatory networks. *Nat. Methods* **20**, 1355–1367 (2023).
46. Kramer, B. A., Sarabia Del Castillo, J. & Pelkmans, L. Multimodal perception links cellular state to decision-making in single cells. *Science* **377**, 642–648 (2022).
47. Weidemüller, P., Kholmatov, M., Petsalaki, E. & Zaugg, J. B. Transcription factors: Bridge between cell signaling and gene regulation. *Proteomics* **21**, e2000034 (2021).
48. Deribe, Y. L., Pawson, T. & Dikic, I. Post-translational modifications in signal integration. *Nat. Struct. Mol. Biol.* **17**, 666–672 (2010).
49. Lun, X.-K. & Bodenmiller, B. Profiling Cell Signaling Networks at Single-cell Resolution. *Mol. Cell. Proteomics* **19**, 744–756 (2020).
50. Dugourd, A. & Saez-Rodriguez, J. Footprint-based functional analysis of multiomic data. *Current Opinion in Systems Biology* **15**, 82–90 (2019).

51. Rydenfelt, M., Klinger, B., Klünemann, M. & Blüthgen, N. SPEED2: inferring upstream pathway activity from differential gene expression. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **48**, W307–W312 (2020).

52. Jiang, P. *et al.* Systematic investigation of cytokine signaling activity at the tissue and single-cell levels. *Nat. Methods* **18**, 1181–1191 (2021).

This work introduced a comprehensive resource describing how cytokines affect gene expression which can be used to infer cytokine activity from transcriptomics data.

53. Garrido-Rodriguez, M., Zirngibl, K., Ivanova, O., Lobentanzer, S. & Saez-Rodriguez, J. Integrating knowledge and omics to decipher mechanisms via large-scale models of signaling networks. *Mol. Syst. Biol.* **18**, e11036 (2022).

54. Dimitrov, D. *et al.* Comparison of methods and resources for cell-cell communication inference from single-cell RNA-Seq data. *Nat. Commun.* **13**, 3224 (2022).

55. Vento-Tormo, R. *et al.* Single-cell reconstruction of the early maternal-fetal interface in humans. *Nature* **563**, 347–353 (2018).

This work introduced a popular tool for cell-cell communication analysis, which they used to systematically study immune-regulatory mechanisms in the maternal–fetal interface.

56. Browaeys, R., Saelens, W. & Saeys, Y. NicheNet: modeling intercellular communication by linking ligands to target genes. *Nat. Methods* **17**, 159–162 (2020).

This work introduced a broadly used tools to analyze cell-cell communication analysis by integrating intracellular signaling networks.

57. Zhang, Y. *et al.* A T cell resilience model associated with response to immunotherapy in multiple tumor types. *Nat. Med.* **28**, 1421–1431 (2022).
58. Wilk, A. J., Shalek, A. K., Holmes, S. & Blish, C. A. Comparative analysis of cell–cell communication at single-cell resolution. *Nat. Biotechnol.* (2023) doi:10.1038/s41587-023-01782-z.
59. Raredon, M. S. B. *et al.* Comprehensive visualization of cell-cell interactions in single-cell and spatial transcriptomics with NICHES. *Bioinformatics* **39**, (2023). doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btac775
60. Zinner, M., Lukonin, I. & Liberali, P. Design principles of tissue organisation: How single cells coordinate across scales. *Curr. Opin. Cell Biol.* **67**, 37–45 (2020).
61. Luthria, G., Lauffenburger, D. & Miller, M. A. Cell-Cell Communication Networks in Tissue: Toward Quantitatively Linking Structure with Function. *Current Opinion in Systems Biology* (2021) doi:10.1016/j.coisb.2021.05.002.
62. Graham, D. B. & Xavier, R. J. Conditioning of the immune system by the microbiome. *Trends Immunol.* **44**, 499–511 (2023).
63. Zhang, B., Vogelzang, A. & Fagarasan, S. Secreted immune metabolites that mediate immune cell communication and function. *Trends Immunol.* **43**, 990–1005 (2022).

64. Zheng, R. *et al.* MEBOCOST: Metabolic Cell-Cell Communication Modeling by Single Cell Transcriptome. *BioRxiv* (2022) doi:10.1101/2022.05.30.494067.
65. Dimitrov, D. *et al.* LIANA+: an all-in-one cell-cell communication framework. *BioRxiv* (2023) doi:10.1101/2023.08.19.553863.
66. Zhao, W., Johnston, K. G., Ren, H., Xu, X. & Nie, Q. Inferring neuron-neuron communications from single-cell transcriptomics through NeuronChat. *Nat. Commun.* **14**, 1128 (2023).
67. Armingol, E., Larsen, R. O., Cequeira, M., Baghdassarian, H. & Lewis, N. E. Unraveling the coordinated dynamics of protein- and metabolite-mediated cell-cell communication. *BioRxiv* (2022) doi:10.1101/2022.11.02.514917.
68. Cui, A. *et al.* Dictionary of immune responses to cytokines at single-cell resolution. *Nature* (2023) doi:10.1038/s41586-023-06816-9.
69. Liu, Z., Sun, D. & Wang, C. Evaluation of cell-cell interaction methods by integrating single-cell RNA sequencing data with spatial information. *Genome Biol.* **23**, 218 (2022).
70. Browaeys, R. *et al.* MultiNicheNet: a flexible framework for differential cell-cell communication analysis from multi-sample multi-condition single-cell transcriptomics data. *BioRxiv* (2023) doi:10.1101/2023.06.13.544751.
71. Armingol, E. *et al.* Context-aware deconvolution of cell-cell communication with Tensor-cell2cell. *Nat. Commun.* **13**, 3665 (2022).

72. Chua, R. L. *et al.* COVID-19 severity correlates with airway epithelium-immune cell interactions identified by single-cell analysis. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **38**, 970–979 (2020).
73. Nasab, R. Z. *et al.* Deep Learning in Spatially Resolved Transcriptomics: A Comprehensive Technical View. *arXiv* (2022) doi:10.48550/arxiv.2210.04453.
74. Li, B. *et al.* Benchmarking spatial and single-cell transcriptomics integration methods for transcript distribution prediction and cell type deconvolution. *Nat. Methods* **19**, 662–670 (2022).
75. Dries, R. *et al.* Giotto: a toolbox for integrative analysis and visualization of spatial expression data. *Genome Biol.* **22**, 78 (2021).
76. Garcia-Alonso, L. *et al.* Mapping the temporal and spatial dynamics of the human endometrium in vivo and in vitro. *Nat. Genet.* **53**, 1698–1711 (2021).
77. Shao, X. *et al.* Knowledge-graph-based cell-cell communication inference for spatially resolved transcriptomic data with SpaTalk. *Nat. Commun.* **13**, 4429 (2022).
78. Li, Z., Wang, T., Liu, P. & Huang, Y. SpatialDM: Rapid identification of spatially co-expressed ligand-receptor reveals cell-cell communication patterns. *BioRxiv* (2022) doi:10.1101/2022.08.19.504616.
79. Cang, Z. *et al.* Screening cell-cell communication in spatial transcriptomics via collective optimal transport. *Nat. Methods* **20**, 218–228 (2023).

80. Frede, A. *et al.* B cell expansion hinders the stroma-epithelium regenerative cross talk during mucosal healing. *Immunity* **55**, 2336-2351.e12 (2022).
81. Lin, J.-R. *et al.* Multiplexed 3D atlas of state transitions and immune interaction in colorectal cancer. *Cell* **186**, 363-381.e19 (2023).
82. Bock, C. *et al.* High-content CRISPR screening. *Nat. Rev. Methods Primers* **2**, 8 (2022).
83. Kustatscher, G. *et al.* Understudied proteins: opportunities and challenges for functional proteomics. *Nat. Methods* **19**, 774–779 (2022).
84. Stražar, M. *et al.* HLA-II immunopeptidome profiling and deep learning reveal features of antigenicity to inform antigen discovery. *Immunity* **56**, 1681-1698.e13 (2023).
85. Huffman, R. G. *et al.* Prioritized mass spectrometry increases the depth, sensitivity and data completeness of single-cell proteomics. *Nat. Methods* **20**, 714–722 (2023).
86. Makhmut, A. *et al.* A framework for ultra-low input spatial tissue proteomics. *bioRxiv* (2023).
87. Rappez, L. *et al.* SpaceM reveals metabolic states of single cells. *Nat. Methods* **18**, 799–805 (2021).
88. Vicari, M. *et al.* Spatial multimodal analysis of transcriptomes and metabolomes in tissues. *Nat. Biotechnol.* (2023) doi:10.1038/s41587-023-01937-y.

89. Deng, Y. *et al.* Spatial profiling of chromatin accessibility in mouse and human tissues. *Nature* **609**, 375–383 (2022).
90. Zhang, D. *et al.* Spatial epigenome-transcriptome co-profiling of mammalian tissues. *Nature* **616**, 113–122 (2023).
91. Engblom, C. *et al.* Spatial transcriptomics of T and B cell receptors uncovers lymphocyte clonal dynamics in human tissue. *BioRxiv* (2022) doi:10.1101/2022.11.22.516865.
92. Liu, Y. *et al.* High-plex protein and whole transcriptome co-mapping at cellular resolution with spatial CITE-seq. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **41**, 1405–1409 (2023).
93. Lötstedt, B., Stražar, M., Xavier, R., Regev, A. & Vickovic, S. Spatial host-microbiome sequencing reveals niches in the mouse gut. *Nat. Biotechnol.* (2023) doi:10.1038/s41587-023-01988-1.
94. Saarenpää, S. *et al.* Spatial metatranscriptomics resolves host-bacteria-fungi interactomes. *Nat. Biotechnol.* (2023) doi:10.1038/s41587-023-01979-2.
95. Udani, S. *et al.* Secretion encoded single-cell sequencing (SEC-seq) uncovers gene expression signatures associated with high VEGF-A secretion in mesenchymal stromal cells. *BioRxiv* (2023) doi:10.1101/2023.01.07.523110.
96. Zhang, S. *et al.* Monitoring of cell-cell communication and contact history in mammals. *Science* **378**, eabo5503 (2022).

97. Clark, I. C. *et al.* Barcoded viral tracing of single-cell interactions in central nervous system inflammation. *Science* **372**, eabf1230 (2021).
98. Hor, J. L. & Germain, R. N. Intravital and high-content multiplex imaging of the immune system. *Trends Cell Biol.* **32**, 406–420 (2022).
99. Chen, W. *et al.* Live-seq enables temporal transcriptomic recording of single cells. *Nature* **608**, 733–740 (2022).
100. Kunes, R. Z., Walle, T., Nawy, T. & Pe'er, D. Supervised discovery of interpretable gene programs from single-cell data. *BioRxiv* (2022) doi:10.1101/2022.12.20.521311.
101. Qoku, A. & Buettner, F. Encoding Domain Knowledge in Multi-view Latent Variable Models: A Bayesian Approach with Structured Sparsity. *arXiv* (2022) doi:10.48550/arxiv.2204.06242.
102. Lotfollahi, M. *et al.* Biologically informed deep learning to query gene programs in single-cell atlases. *Nat. Cell Biol.* **25**, 337–350 (2023).
103. OpenAI. GPT-4 Technical Report. *arXiv* (2023) doi:10.48550/arxiv.2303.08774.
104. Cui, H., Wang, C., Maan, H. & Wang, B. scGPT: Towards Building a Foundation Model for Single-Cell Multi-omics Using Generative AI. *BioRxiv* (2023) doi:10.1101/2023.04.30.538439.
105. Theodoris, C. V. *et al.* Transfer learning enables predictions in network biology. *Nature* **618**, 616–624 (2023).

106. Vodovotz, Y. *et al.* Solving Immunology? *Trends Immunol.* **38**, 116–127 (2017).
 107. Handel, A., La Gruta, N. L. & Thomas, P. G. Simulation modelling for immunologists. *Nat. Rev. Immunol.* **20**, 186–195 (2020).
 108. Bachireddy, P. *et al.* Mapping the evolution of T cell states during response and resistance to adoptive cellular therapy. *Cell Rep.* **37**, 109992 (2021).
 109. Kuppe, C. *et al.* Spatial multi-omic map of human myocardial infarction. *Nature* **608**, 766–777 (2022).
 110. Kamal, A. *et al.* GRaNIE and GRaNPA: inference and evaluation of enhancer-mediated gene regulatory networks. *Mol. Syst. Biol.* **19**, e11627 (2023).
 111. Kamimoto, K. *et al.* Dissecting cell identity via network inference and in silico gene perturbation. *Nature* **614**, 742–751 (2023).
- This work pioneered GRN inference from paired single-cell sequencing of chromatin accessibility and transcriptome and its use to predict perturbation effect.
112. Kwok, A. J. *et al.* Neutrophils and emergency granulopoiesis drive immune suppression and an extreme response endotype during sepsis. *Nat. Immunol.* **24**, 767–779 (2023).
 113. Han, A., Glanville, J., Hansmann, L. & Davis, M. M. Linking T-cell receptor sequence to functional phenotype at the single-cell level. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **32**, 684–692 (2014).

This work pioneered paired sequencing of the transcriptome and TCR alpha/beta chains in single cells in a high-throughput manner.

114. Pai, J. A. & Satpathy, A. T. High-throughput and single-cell T cell receptor sequencing technologies. *Nat. Methods* **18**, 881–892 (2021).
115. Valkiers, S. *et al.* Recent advances in T-cell receptor repertoire analysis: bridging the gap with multimodal single-cell RNA sequencing. *ImmunoInformatics* 100009 (2022) doi:10.1016/j.immuno.2022.100009.
116. Joglekar, A. V. & Li, G. T cell antigen discovery. *Nat. Methods* **18**, 873–880 (2021).
117. Bradley, P. & Thomas, P. G. Using T cell receptor repertoires to understand the principles of adaptive immune recognition. *Annu. Rev. Immunol.* **37**, 547–570 (2019).
118. Zhang, L. *et al.* Lineage tracking reveals dynamic relationships of T cells in colorectal cancer. *Nature* **564**, 268–272 (2018).
119. Glanville, J. *et al.* Identifying specificity groups in the T cell receptor repertoire. *Nature* **547**, 94–98 (2017).
120. Dash, P. *et al.* Quantifiable predictive features define epitope-specific T cell receptor repertoires. *Nature* **547**, 89–93 (2017).
121. Bassez, A. *et al.* A single-cell map of intratumoral changes during anti-PD1 treatment of patients with breast cancer. *Nat. Med.* **27**, 820–832 (2021).

122. Suo, C. *et al.* Dandelion uses the single-cell adaptive immune receptor repertoire to explore lymphocyte developmental origins. *Nat. Biotechnol.* (2023) doi:10.1038/s41587-023-01734-7.
123. Zhang, Z., Xiong, D., Wang, X., Liu, H. & Wang, T. Mapping the functional landscape of T cell receptor repertoires by single-T cell transcriptomics. *Nat. Methods* **18**, 92–99 (2021).
124. Schattgen, S. A. *et al.* Integrating T cell receptor sequences and transcriptional profiles by clonotype neighbor graph analysis (CoNGA). *Nat. Biotechnol.* **40**, 54–63 (2022).
125. An, Y., Drost, F., Theis, F., Schubert, B. & Lotfollahi, M. Integrating T-cell receptor and transcriptome for large-scale single-cell immune profiling analysis. *BioRxiv* (2021) doi:10.1101/2021.06.24.449733.
126. Zhang, Z. *et al.* Interpreting the B-cell receptor repertoire with single-cell gene expression using Benisse. *Nat. Mach. Intell.* (2022) doi:10.1038/s42256-022-00492-6.
127. Shugay, M. *et al.* VDJdb: a curated database of T-cell receptor sequences with known antigen specificity. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **46**, D419–D427 (2018).
128. Hudson, D., Fernandes, R. A., Basham, M., Ogg, G. & Koohy, H. Can we predict T cell specificity with digital biology and machine learning? *Nat. Rev. Immunol.* **23**, 511–521 (2023).
129. Osumi-Sutherland, D. *et al.* Cell type ontologies of the Human Cell Atlas. *Nat. Cell Biol.* **23**, 1129–1135 (2021).

130. Lotfollahi, M. *et al.* Mapping single-cell data to reference atlases by transfer learning. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **40**, 121–130 (2022).
131. Heimberg, G. *et al.* Scalable querying of human cell atlases via a foundational model reveals commonalities across fibrosis-associated macrophages. *BioRxiv* (2023) doi:10.1101/2023.07.18.549537.
132. Hao, Y. *et al.* Integrated analysis of multimodal single-cell data. *Cell* **184**, 3573–3587. (2021).
133. Jerby-Arnon, L. & Regev, A. DIALOGUE maps multicellular programs in tissue from single-cell or spatial transcriptomics data. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **40**, 1467–1477 (2022).
134. Mitchel, J. *et al.* Tensor decomposition reveals coordinated multicellular patterns of transcriptional variation that distinguish and stratify disease individuals. *BioRxiv* (2022) doi:10.1101/2022.02.16.480703.
135. Ramirez Flores, R. O., Lanzer, J. D., Dimitrov, D., Velten, B. & Saez-Rodriguez, J. Multicellular factor analysis of single-cell data for a tissue-centric understanding of disease. *eLife* **12**, e93161 (2023).
136. Palla, G. *et al.* Squidpy: a scalable framework for spatial omics analysis. *Nat. Methods* **19**, 171–178 (2022).
137. Schapiro, D. *et al.* histoCAT: analysis of cell phenotypes and interactions in multiplex image cytometry data. *Nat. Methods* **14**, 873–876 (2017).

138. Keren, L. *et al.* A Structured Tumor-Immune Microenvironment in Triple Negative Breast Cancer Revealed by Multiplexed Ion Beam Imaging. *Cell* **174**, 1373-1387.e19 (2018).
139. Chen, Z., Soifer, I., Hilton, H., Keren, L. & Jovic, V. Modeling Multiplexed Images with Spatial-LDA Reveals Novel Tissue Microenvironments. *J. Comput. Biol.* **27**, 1204–1218 (2020).
140. Goltsev, Y. *et al.* Deep Profiling of Mouse Splenic Architecture with CODEX Multiplexed Imaging. *Cell* **174**, 968-981.e15 (2018).
141. Schürch, C. M. *et al.* Coordinated cellular neighborhoods orchestrate antitumoral immunity at the colorectal cancer invasive front. *Cell* **182**, 1341-1359.e19 (2020).
142. Wang, X. Q. *et al.* Spatial predictors of immunotherapy response in triple-negative breast cancer. *Nature* **621**, 868–876 (2023).
143. Fischer, D. S., Schaar, A. C. & Theis, F. J. Modeling intercellular communication in tissues using spatial graphs of cells. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **41**, 332–336 (2023).
144. Tanevski, J., Flores, R. O. R., Gabor, A., Schapiro, D. & Saez-Rodriguez, J. Explainable multiview framework for dissecting spatial relationships from highly multiplexed data. *Genome Biol.* **23**, 97 (2022).
145. Wu, Z. *et al.* Graph deep learning for the characterization of tumour microenvironments from spatial protein profiles in tissue specimens. *Nat. Biomed. Eng.* **6**, 1435–1448 (2022).

146. Sinha, S., Eisenhaber, B., Jensen, L. J., Kalbuaji, B. & Eisenhaber, F. Darkness in the human gene and protein function space: widely modest or absent illumination by the life science literature and the trend for fewer protein function discoveries since 2000. *Proteomics* **18**, e1800093 (2018).
147. Lambert, S. A. *et al.* The human transcription factors. *Cell* **172**, 650–665 (2018).
148. Efremova, M., Vento-Tormo, M., Teichmann, S. A. & Vento-Tormo, R. CellPhoneDB: inferring cell-cell communication from combined expression of multi-subunit ligand-receptor complexes. *Nat. Protoc.* **15**, 1484–1506 (2020).
149. Ozaki, K. & Leonard, W. J. Cytokine and cytokine receptor pleiotropy and redundancy. *J. Biol. Chem.* **277**, 29355–29358 (2002).
150. Korn, T. & Hiltensperger, M. Role of IL-6 in the commitment of T cell subsets. *Cytokine* **146**, 155654 (2021).